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12.00.09-УГОЛОВНЫЙ ПРОЦЕСС. КРИМИНАЛИСТИКА, ОПЕРАТИВНО-РОЗЫСКНОЕ ПРАВО И СУДЕБНАЯ ЭКСПЕРТИЗА

Norova Nasiba Azamatovna,
Lecturer of the department International Law and protection of human rights
of Law Enforcement Academy Republic of Uzbekistan
E-mail: liliya.achilova@mail.ru

**THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ENHANCING THE WORK OF
CRIMINAL PROCEDURE SPECIALISTS IN UZBEKISTAN**

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ANNOTATION

This article explores the transformative role of digital technologies in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of criminal procedure specialists in Uzbekistan. The study employs the IMRAD (Introduction, Methods, Results, and Discussion) structure to examine the impact of technological advancements on the criminal justice system, with a focus on digital evidence management, case processing, and communication between law enforcement agencies. The findings suggest that the integration of digital tools significantly improves procedural accuracy and speed, though challenges such as cybersecurity threats and the need for specialized training remain.

Keywords: digital technologies, criminal procedure, efficiency, cybersecurity, evidence, law enforcement agencies, specialized training.

Норова Насиба Азаматовна,
Преподаватель кафедры Международного права и защиты
прав человека Правоохранительной академии Республики Узбекистан
E-mail: liliya.achilova@mail.ru

**РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УСОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ
СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ ПО УГОЛОВНОМУ ПРОЦЕССУ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается преобразующая роль цифровых технологий в повышении эффективности и результативности работы специалистов по уголовному процессу в Узбекистане. Исследование проводится с использованием структуры IMRAD (Введение, Методы, Результаты и Обсуждение) для анализа влияния технологических достижений на

систему уголовного правосудия, с особым акцентом на управление цифровыми доказательствами, обработку дел и коммуникацию между правоохранительными органами. Результаты показывают, что интеграция цифровых инструментов значительно улучшает точность и скорость процедур, однако остаются вызовы, такие как угрозы кибербезопасности и необходимость специализированного обучения.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, уголовный процесс, эффективность, кибербезопасность, доказательства, правоохранительные органы, специализированное обучение.

Норова Насиба Азаматовна,
 Ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш академияси
 Халқаро ҳуқуқ ва инсон ҳуқуқларини
 ҳимоя қилиш кафедраси ўқитувчиси
 E-mail: liliya.achilova@mail.ru

ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ЖИНОЯТ ПРОЦЕССЛАРИ МУТАХАССИСЛАРИ ФАОЛИЯТИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШДА РАҚАМЛИ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақола Ўзбекистонда жиноят процесслари мутахассисларининг самарадорлиги ва натижадорлигини оширишда рақамли технологияларнинг ўзгарувчан ролини тадқиқ қилинади. Тадқиқот IMRAD (Кириш, Усуллар, Натийжалар ва Мунозара) тузилмасидан фойдаланиб, технологик тараққиётнинг жиноят-адлия тизимида таъсирини, жумладан, рақамли далилларни бошқариш, иш юритиш ва ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш органлари ўртасидаги алоқани ўрганади. Натийжалар шуни кўрсатадики, рақамли воситаларнинг интеграцияси жараёнларнинг аниқлиги ва тезлигини сезиларли даражада яхшилайдди, аммо киберхавфсизлик таҳдидлари ва махсус тайёргарликка бўлган эҳтиёж каби муаммолар мавжуд.

Калит сўзлар: рақамли технологиялар, жиноят процесси, самарадорлик, киберхавфсизлик, далиллар, ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш органлари, махсус тайёргарлик.

Introduction

The criminal justice system in Uzbekistan, like in many other countries, is undergoing significant changes due to the rapid advancement of digital technologies. The introduction of digital tools has the potential to revolutionize the work of criminal procedure specialists by improving the efficiency and accuracy of legal processes. In recent years, the adoption of these technologies has become crucial in managing the complexities of modern criminal cases, particularly with the rise in cybercrime and the growing volume of digital evidence. The value system enshrined in the Constitution of Uzbekistan, encourages, at the level of criminal law, to provide maximum opportunity for citizens who have come into conflict with the law correct in a timely manner and direct your efforts to preventing possible harm to society or elimination of harm already caused, or its minimization.

In this aspect, the President of our country Shavkat is right Mirziyoyev, who notes that "...no matter how perfect the laws we create, no matter what reforms we carry out, if our citizens will not have enough legal knowledge and culture, we will not we will be able to achieve the expected results" [1].

In recent years, Uzbekistan has embarked on a path of comprehensive reform within its criminal justice system. A significant component of this reform is the liberalization of criminal policy, particularly through the expansion of incentive norms within criminal law. Incentive norms play a crucial role in promoting compliance with the law by offering legal benefits, such as reduced sentences or exemptions from liability, to individuals who cooperate with law enforcement or demonstrate genuine remorse. The necessity of such reforms is underscored by the Presidential

Decree No. PP-3723 issued on May 14, 2018, which explicitly identifies the limited and ineffective application of incentive norms as a critical shortcoming in the existing criminal and criminal procedure legislation [2]. This article aims to explore the role of digital technologies in enhancing the work of criminal procedure specialists in Uzbekistan, focusing on their impact on case management, evidence processing, and inter-agency communication.

Methods

This study adopts a qualitative research approach, utilizing case studies, legal document analysis, and interviews with criminal procedure specialists in Uzbekistan. The selection of case studies was based on the implementation of digital technologies in high-profile criminal cases in Uzbekistan over the past five years. Legal documents, including laws, regulations, and procedural guidelines, were analyzed to understand the legal framework governing the use of digital tools in criminal procedures. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with prosecutors, defense attorneys, and judges to gain insights into the practical challenges and benefits associated with the use of digital technologies in criminal justice. A comparative approach is utilized to examine the application of incentive norms in other jurisdictions, particularly in countries that have successfully implemented similar reforms. Additionally, legal doctrines and scholarly articles on the topic of criminal law reform and the use of incentive norms are reviewed to provide a theoretical framework for the discussion.

Results

The analysis reveals that digital technologies have significantly improved various aspects of criminal procedure in Uzbekistan. One of the key areas of impact is digital evidence management. The introduction of digital evidence management systems (DEMS) has streamlined the collection, storage, and analysis of digital evidence, reducing the risk of evidence tampering and loss. Additionally, the use of digital case management systems (CMS) has expedited the processing of cases, allowing for more efficient tracking of case progress and deadlines.

Moreover, digital communication platforms have enhanced coordination between law enforcement agencies, prosecutors, and courts, leading to more cohesive and timely decision-making processes. The integration of digital tools has also facilitated the remote participation of legal professionals in hearings, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, ensuring the continuity of judicial proceedings without compromising public health.

However, the study also identifies several challenges associated with the implementation of digital technologies in criminal procedure. These include cybersecurity risks, the need for continuous updates and maintenance of digital systems, and the requirement for specialized training for legal professionals to effectively utilize these tools.

By the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 23, 2019 the criminal procedure legislation has been amended, concerning the use of videoconferencing in criminal proceedings. This computer technology has made it possible to conduct trials at a considerable distance when the court and the convicted person are far from each other. Positive aspects can be noted when consideration of a criminal case in videoconferencing mode: possibility witnesses, victims, who are outside the territory where is undergoing a trial in order to save their funds, participate in court and testify at the place of residence, the likelihood of interviewing additional witnesses in court for establishing the truth in the case, reducing the time for consideration of cases.

The Presidential Decree No. PP-3723 represents a significant policy shift towards a more liberal approach in the application of criminal law in Uzbekistan. The decree acknowledges that the current criminal and criminal procedure legislation does not sufficiently leverage incentive norms, which could otherwise play a pivotal role in the criminal justice system. The expansion of these norms is recommended as a means to encourage rehabilitation and reintegration of offenders, reduce recidivism, and enhance overall compliance with the law [2].

One of the key proposals under this decree is the broader application of norms that allow for the mitigation of punishment or the complete release of individuals from criminal liability under certain conditions. This approach aligns with international best practices, where incentive norms have been effectively used to achieve more equitable outcomes in the criminal justice system. Moreover,

the decree suggests the need for further refinement of the legal provisions that determine the circumstances under which the criminality of an act may be excluded, such as in cases of self-defense or necessity.

Singapore was the first country to develop and implement electronic justice systems. The experience of Singapore is now being studied by countries worldwide that are integrating digital technologies into their judicial systems. Initially, Singaporean authorities created an electronic justice system focused on traffic law enforcement. This allowed them to gain experience and address the challenges that arose with the operation of a specialized system. Following this, the use of digital technologies was expanded to civil and criminal proceedings, enabling a phased transition to a fully digital format for resolving all types of cases.

Singapore's pioneering efforts in the digitization of its judicial system have set a global benchmark. The country's e-justice system, known as the Integrated Electronic Litigation (E-Litigation) system, now serves as a comprehensive platform that supports the entire litigation process - from filing to judgment - in an online environment. The system facilitates the submission of documents, case management, and even remote hearings, significantly enhancing the efficiency and accessibility of the courts.

Furthermore, Singapore's success in digitalizing its judicial processes is not just limited to traffic, civil, and criminal cases. The system has been expanded to handle family law, small claims, and even arbitration cases, demonstrating the versatility and scalability of their digital justice framework. The Singaporean model emphasizes user-friendly interfaces, robust cybersecurity measures, and continuous updates to accommodate new legal challenges and technological advancements.

Singapore's journey also underscores the importance of stakeholder engagement and training. The judiciary, legal professionals, and the public were gradually introduced to the new system, with extensive training programs to ensure smooth adoption. This methodical approach ensured that the transition to a digital justice system did not disrupt the administration of justice but rather enhanced it.

By setting a precedent in the digitalization of justice, Singapore has become a global leader in this domain, providing valuable insights and a model framework for other countries aiming to modernize their judicial systems [3].

Digital technologies are playing an increasingly significant role in reforming and improving the effectiveness of law enforcement systems around the world. India, as one of the largest democracies, is actively integrating technology into its legal and criminal justice system, which can significantly improve communication between various government agencies and speed up the enforcement process.

Technological interaction between the police and external agencies India has introduced a system of technological interaction between the police and various external institutions such as prisons, courts, transport services, passport offices, foreigners registration departments and others. This interaction is facilitated through integrated digital platforms that provide timely access to relevant information and support the seamless flow of data between institutions.

These systems significantly improve the speed and accuracy of criminal justice professionals, reducing the time spent collecting and sharing information. For example, the integration of police databases with prison systems and judicial authorities allows for the instant exchange of information about prisoners, their legal status and the progress of court cases. This not only speeds up the investigation process, but also reduces the likelihood of human error [4].

Another important tool that helps improve the work of criminal procedure specialists is the online library of procedural decisions. In India, such a library contains investigation checklists, answers to key questions related to criminal investigations, archives of court decisions, and instructions for police officers.

This online library serves as a valuable resource for professionals, providing access to up-to-date, trusted information at any time. For example, during an investigation, specialists can quickly gain access to relevant legal precedents, which helps them make informed decisions. The library also

allows for standardization of approaches to investigations, which leads to greater consistency and fairness in criminal legal practice [5].

The integration of digital technologies into law enforcement also includes the use of analytical platforms based on artificial intelligence (AI) to predict and prevent crime. India has begun to implement systems that analyze huge amounts of data collected from various sources and predict potential areas of criminal activity. This allows law enforcement agencies to take action in advance, which greatly increases the efficiency of their work.

Additionally, digitalization of law enforcement in India includes the use of mobile applications to interact with citizens. The apps allow citizens to report crimes, get information about the progress of their cases and consult with lawyers without having to visit police stations or courts. This not only facilitates citizens' access to justice, but also makes the work of criminal trial specialists more transparent and accountable [6].

Discussion

The findings of this study highlight the transformative potential of digital technologies in the field of criminal procedure in Uzbekistan. The adoption of digital evidence management systems and case management systems has not only increased the efficiency of legal processes but also enhanced the accuracy and integrity of criminal investigations. By minimizing the risk of human error and reducing the time required to process cases, these technologies contribute to a more effective criminal justice system.

Furthermore, the use of digital communication platforms has proven essential in maintaining the functionality of the criminal justice system during unprecedented times, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The ability to conduct remote hearings and meetings has ensured that legal processes continue without significant delays, upholding the principles of timely justice [7].

Despite these advancements, the study underscores the importance of addressing the challenges associated with digital technologies in criminal procedure. Cybersecurity threats pose a significant risk to the confidentiality and integrity of digital evidence, necessitating the implementation of robust security measures. Additionally, the rapid pace of technological change requires ongoing training and education for criminal procedure specialists to keep pace with new developments.

The expansion of incentive norms within the criminal justice system of Uzbekistan represents a strategic move towards a more humane and rehabilitative approach to criminal justice. By offering legal incentives for cooperation and good behavior, the state not only encourages lawful conduct but also facilitates the reintegration of offenders into society. However, the successful implementation of these reforms requires careful consideration of the legal and social contexts in which they operate. Challenges such as potential misuse of these norms, the need for judicial training, and the development of clear guidelines for their application must be addressed to ensure the effectiveness of the reforms [8].

The introduction of digital technologies into the Indian criminal legal system is already producing significant results, improving the interaction between various institutions and increasing the overall efficiency of law enforcement [9]. However, along with achievements, challenges remain, such as the need to train specialists, ensure cybersecurity and adapt the regulatory framework to new technologies. However, the Indian experience demonstrates that digitalization is an integral element of modern criminal justice, and its further development will play a key role in improving the quality of work of criminal justice professionals [10].

Proposals:

1. Development of Infrastructure and Training: It is necessary to strengthen the digital technology infrastructure in criminal justice and ensure systematic training of specialists. This will maximize the efficiency of digital tools and reduce risks associated with their use.

2. Implementation of Cybersecurity Standards: To protect digital evidence and information used in criminal proceedings, it is essential to develop and implement national cybersecurity standards adapted to Uzbekistan's conditions. This could include the use of data encryption, multi-factor authentication, and other modern technologies.

3. **Strengthening the Legal Framework:** For the successful application of digital technologies in criminal justice, it is necessary to review and supplement the existing legal framework, taking into account new challenges and opportunities provided by modern technologies. This also involves creating legal mechanisms to protect the rights and interests of participants in criminal proceedings in the digital environment.

4. **International Cooperation and Exchange of Experience:** Uzbekistan should enhance cooperation with other countries and international organizations involved in the digitalization of criminal justice. Sharing experiences and best practices will accelerate the implementation of effective solutions and minimize potential risks.

5. **Creation of a Competence Center for Digital Technologies in Justice:** A special competence center should be established to develop and implement innovative digital solutions in criminal proceedings. This center could also provide training and certification for specialists and conduct research on relevant issues related to the digitalization of criminal justice.

Conclusion:

The ongoing liberalization in Uzbekistan's criminal policy, as evidenced by Presidential Decree No. PP-3723, marks a critical step towards modernizing the country's criminal justice system. The expansion of incentive norms offers a promising avenue for reducing crime, promoting rehabilitation, and ensuring justice. However, the success of these reforms will depend on the careful implementation and continuous evaluation of their impact on the legal system and society at large.

Based on the conducted research, the following conclusions have been made:

1. **Enhancing the Efficiency of the Justice Process:** Digital technologies have significantly improved the accuracy and speed of the criminal process in Uzbekistan. The integration of tools such as digital evidence management systems and electronic case management systems has streamlined procedures and minimized human errors, leading to more efficient and faster handling of criminal cases.

2. **Strengthening Cooperation Between Law Enforcement Agencies:** Digital communication platforms have facilitated better coordination among various law enforcement agencies, prosecutors, and courts, resulting in more coordinated and timely decisions. This has been particularly important during the COVID-19 pandemic, where remote court hearings became essential.

3. **Cybersecurity Challenges:** Despite the clear advantages, the use of digital technologies comes with serious cybersecurity threats. These threats can compromise the confidentiality and integrity of digital evidence, highlighting the need for robust data protection measures.

4. **The Need for Specialized Training:** The implementation of digital technologies requires new knowledge and skills from criminal procedure specialists. The lack of specialized training could hinder the effective use of these technologies, necessitating continuous updates in knowledge and skills.

In conclusion, while digital technologies offer substantial benefits to the criminal justice system in Uzbekistan, their successful implementation requires careful consideration of the associated risks and challenges. Continued investment in technology, infrastructure, and training will be essential to fully realize the potential of digital tools in enhancing the work of criminal procedure specialists.

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